

E-books Technology

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Introduction

Rubin (2016) defines an e-book as a non-editable book that is created or converted into a digital format such that it can be read on digital devices or downloaded through any digital format such as PDF, EPUB, and AZW. This availability in several forms eases its distribution across several devices and software. The main characteristic of e-books that differentiate them from other documents is that they should not be editable, and they must be reflowable such that their display can fit the size of any screen. Wahl (2018) explains e-books have several advantages compared to traditional book forms since they save on space and money. E-books are also convenient, more portable, and they save on the environment since they are paperless. The ease of downloading e-books also means that they are easily transferrable across many users (Wahl, 2018). This study will analyze case studies of implementations of e-books in different libraries and the impact that the technology has had.

Summary of case studies

According to Maceviciute et al. (2017), the development of e-books has led to a significant shift in the market by increasing the capacity of libraries without requiring intensive capital injections. Libraries have transformed how they acquire and utilize resources after the advent of e-books. Maceviciute et al. (2017) also explain that e-books have changed the relationship between libraries and booksellers such that publishers now incorporate an aggregator rather than going through booksellers. An aggregator is a commercial e-book provider under a publishing company (Maceviciute et al. 2017).

Ritchie & Skoglund (2015) provide a case study that compares the usage of e-books and print books in Barwon Health Library, Victoria, Australia. According to this study, the use of e-books has been on the rise since 2012. In contrast, print book usage has either been static or declining (Ritchie & Skoglund, 2015). However, the usage of e-books depended on their availability, accessibility, and flexibility of their formats. However, Ritchie & Skoglund (2015) note that the main factor that hampered the use of e-books in the library was the cost of the download, which almost doubled the price of loaning a print book. However, this cost did not deter many users who preferred having the e-book permanently rather than loaning a print book for a limited time.

According to Tenzin & Yadav (2016), e-books are yet to reach critical mass usage, especially in school libraries, although many other libraries have already adopted the technology. In such libraries, print book formats remain dominant as the libraries are reluctant to incorporate e-books in their collection (Wells & Sallenbach, 2015). However, the study noted that the acceptance of e-books in these libraries would be on par with that of print books by 2020. Those libraries that have incorporated the technology have experienced significant benefits and transformation (Tenzin & Yadav, 2016). In their study in the National Educational Society (NES) International School in India, Tenzin & Yadav (2016) note that the usage of e-books became widespread after the popularization of the technology's benefits. This study concludes that the majority of the students are more comfortable with using e-books rather than print books, primarily due to the accessibility of the former.

Lamani et al. (2018) review a case of open access e-books in social science libraries. Open access research resources, including e-books, have revolutionized scholarly communication by bridging the physical and time barrier and reducing the costs of accessing

information. Piwowar et al. (2018) also concur that e-books have transformed several research fields by readily availing relevant information whenever it is needed. The Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB) now contains numerous e-books ranging across multiple fields (Lamani et al., 2018). The nature of open access in DOAB enables concrete research in these fields.

According to Piwowar et al. (2018), the development of DOAB and other open access platforms has been growing over the last fifteen years since funding institutions are now mandating grantees to publish their studies as free access. These grantees include the US National Institute of Health, Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation, European Commission, and the US National Science Foundation (Piwowar et al., 2018). The creation of large databases and user networks like DOAB has also pushed the emergence of open access e-books in research fields (Piwowar et al., 2018). Libraries are also incorporating these databases in their collection. Free access e-books have thus revolutionized multiple fields.

Conclusion

E-books are a revolutionary technology that has transformed libraries. E-books have multiple advantages, and in particular, accessibility and availability, which have enhanced their adoption in numerous libraries. In the review of the case studies above, e-books' adoption and usage in libraries have been on a consistent rise in several libraries. However, this study has established that the usage of e-books technologies in school libraries has lagged. The main hindrance of incorporating the technology in these libraries is the reluctance to shift from print books. However, for libraries that have added e-books, the usage and adoption of the same by library users have been very high.

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